

Report

September 20-22, 2023
Alcalá de Henares, Spain

European Union

European Regional
Development Fund - ERDF

"A way of making Europe"

GGOS Days 2023

Report

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1 General Information

Date / Time: **September 20-22, 2023**
Website: <https://ggos.org/event/ggos-days-2023/>
Venue: **IGN office in the Campus of the University**
Address: C. Escultor Claudio, 6A, 28805 Alcalá de Henares, Madrid, Spain

2 Program at a glance

The graphic displays the event schedule for Wednesday, Thursday, and Friday. It features a dark blue background with a light blue and green gradient on the right side. A stylized globe is visible on the left edge. The text is white and yellow, listing the time and activity for each day.

Wednesday, September 20th

- 09:00 Opening Session
- 10:30 Recent Activities within IAG and GGOS
- 11:30 Keynote Speaker Session
- 14:10 GGOS Affiliates
- 15:00 Technical Visit of Yebes Observatory

Thursday, September 21st

- 09:00 GGOS External Activities
- 10:30 Making Geodetic Data & Products FAIR
- 11:15 Bureau of Networks and Observations
- 14:15 Bureau of Products and Standards
- 16:00 Splinter Meeting: GGOS Implementation Plan
- 18:00 Visit of Alcalá de Henares

Friday, September 22nd

- 09:00 GGOS Focus Areas
- 11:20 Closing Session

3 Report of the Conference

GGOS convenes its various components annually to report on achievements and formulate activities for the future. On this occasion, the Instituto Geográfico Nacional of Spain hosted the GGOS Days in Alcalá de Henares from 20th to 22nd September 2023. The meeting was hybrid, enabling remote participation, and had 192 attendees, 40 of whom were present in person.

The conference agenda included 10 sessions, beginning with a presentation by Spanish and Portuguese colleagues outlining the current status and future plans for space geodesy in their respective countries. Noteworthy was the informed decision to install the GGOS Affiliate Iberatlantic. The **keynote speaker session** featured three pertinent contributions on interesting geodetic subjects: (1) The contribution of superconducting gravimetry to Earth System observations; (2) Hydrodynamic levelling for modelling hydrodynamics in coastal regions; and (3) Glacial isostatic adjustment and its significance in geodesy. Additionally, a presentation on the usage of K-Band (24 GHz) in geodesy was given.

As **GGOS Affiliate Japan** celebrates its 10th anniversary, its major accomplishment is deploying the latest technology in Japanese fundamental geodetic observatories. The **GGOS Affiliate D-A-CH** focuses on creating methodologies that combine and integrate all geodetic techniques consistently. This goal enhances the precision and dependability of geodetic outcomes.

The **GGOS External Activities** presentations highlighted recent accomplishments of the UN Subcommittee on Geodesy, perspectives for South America's involvement in GGOS, and the collaborative efforts of the IAG's Communication and Outreach Branch and the Coordinating Office of GGOS to enhance the visibility of the IAG and Geodesy. Initiatives **promoting the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data principles** within the IAG were extensively discussed. Specifically, the utilization of DOIs for geodetic data and products and the implementation of the GGOS portal as a convenient one-stop-shop for all geodetic products from IAG and its various components were emphasized.

In the **GGOS Bureau of Networks and Observations (BNO)** session, the IAG Services presented recent achievements and new challenges objectively. This session provided a comprehensive overview of current Service activities. Additionally, the **Committee PLATO** (Performance Simulations and Architectural Trade-

Offs) presented an update on recent simulations aimed at enhancing the geometric configuration of space geodetic reference stations. The **Committee on Satellite Missions** provided an assessment of the technical features and application areas of the newly sanctioned gravity mission MAGIC (Mass change and geoscience international constellation). The **Committee on Data and Information Systems** reported on the progress in deploying GeodesyML (Geodesy Markup Language), a tool that simplifies the manipulation of geodetic data and metadata, including those related to equipment, site logs, measurement, adjustment, quality, monuments, reference frames, and data lineage. The GGOS/IERS joint working group on **Site Survey and Colocation** shared information about the local ties that have been measured at 20 stations since 2020. The number of intra-technique vectors increased from 212 to 253.

At the **GGOS Bureau of Products and Standards (BPS)** session, after an overview presentation showing objectives, structure and activities of this Bureau, interesting discussions about the computation of a **new reference level ellipsoid** and the implementation of a catalogue with **Essential Geodetic Variables** were conducted. This session closed with a review of the **Committee Contributions to Earth System Modelling**.

Regarding the **GGOS Focus Areas (FA)**, the **FA Unified Height System** presented a final report about the integration of its activities into the IAG Commission 2 (Gravity Field) and the IGFS (International Gravity Field Service). This FA was dissolved at the General Assembly of the IUGG (International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics) in Berlin in July 2023, having achieved its objectives. The **FA on Geohazards** presented a status report focused on the advancement of GNSS-based Tsunami Early Warning Systems (GTEWS) and the establishment of a GTEWS capability for the South Pacific's Oceania region. The **FA on Geodetic Space Weather Research** summarized accomplishments in four research areas, namely: the coupling processes among the magnetosphere, thermosphere and ionosphere; modelling of the electron density;

development of thermosphere models; and comprehension of space weather events and their supervising through satellite missions. The recently established **FA on Artificial Intelligence for Geodesy (AI4G)** reported on strategies for the development and evaluation of improved geodetic products based on AI and machine learning. Specific presentations on AI for GNSS remote sensing, gravity field and mass change, prediction of Earth orientation parameters, and geodetic deformation monitoring were given. In addition,

the topics and objectives of two new potential focus areas on the **combination of tropospheric parameters** and the **integrated analysis of GNSS and InSAR** data were discussed.

The remaining sessions were devoted to redefining the memberships of the GGOS management structure, following the customary practice within the IAG every four years.

We extend our sincerest gratitude to the **Instituto Geográfico Nacional** and the **Yebes Observatory** staff for their unwavering commitment in organizing this successful meeting. Moreover, we are thankful to the numerous **speakers** who, through their dedication and hard work, make GGOS possible. We would also like to thank all **participants** for their interest and active contribution to the discussion. Finally, we express our special gratitude to the **IAG Office** for providing travel awards to some participants, enabling them to attend this event.

4 Report of the technical visit to the Yebes Observatory

The GGOS Days 2023 featured a **technical visit to the Yebes Observatory**, a notable scientific facility focused on astronomical and geodetic research and observation, and a key contributor to the IAG and its Services. The Yebes Observatory staff conducted a comprehensive tour of the recently installed equipment and facilities for the conference attendees over the course of an entire afternoon. The visit to the Observatory was rounded off with an informal dinner of Spanish paella, one of the most famous dishes in Spanish cuisine. The exceptional professionalism and friendly welcome of our colleagues at Yebes Observatory created an unforgettable visit.

The Yebes Observatory is equipped with a wide range of instruments, including two VLBI radio telescopes (the 40-metre and the 13.2-metre VGOS telescope) a SLR station, several GNSS stations and a gravimetry pavilion. In addition to the instruments, the Yebes Observatory has several laboratories and workshops.

In particular, it has a laboratory for cryogenic microwave amplifiers and passive devices, a laboratory for cryogenic radio astronomy receptors, a laboratory for electronics and detection devices, an electrochemistry laboratory, a laboratory for measuring microwave feeds (anechoic chamber), and two workshops with precision machining tools, including lathes, 5-axis machines and CNC (Computerized Numerical Control) machines, as well as general machining and metrology instruments. There is also a molecular spectroscopy laboratory that uses radio astronomy receivers and legacy astronomical observation instruments: a 14m radio telescope, a double astrograph, and a solar telescope.

As a highlight, the GGOS Days participants had the opportunity to visit the YLARA (Yebes Laser Ranging) station. The station is in the phase of commissioning and will start regular SLR operation by early 2024. Upon completion of the construction of YLARA, the Yebes Observatory will become the first fundamental geodetic station in Spain, hosting 3 major space geodetic techniques and a local-tie network to interconnect them. YLARA will also be able to track space debris.

5 Visit to Alcalá de Henares and Group Dinner

The local organizers (IGN Spain) prepared a guided tour of the city centre. Alcalá de Henares has a long and fascinating history. The city dates back to Roman times, when it was known as Complutum. It thrived as an important Roman city and later became an Episcopal seat during the Visigothic period. In the 8th century, it fell under Moorish rule but was recaptured by the Christians during the Reconquista.

The city experienced a significant period of cultural and intellectual growth during the Renaissance when Cardinal Cisneros founded the University of Alcalá in 1499. This prestigious institution attracted scholars and thinkers, including the famous writer Miguel de Cervantes, who was born in Alcalá de Henares in 1547. Today, the city proudly preserves its rich heritage and is a UNESCO World Heritage Site, attracting visitors with its historical charm and literary significance. After the impressive guided tour through the city center of Alcalá de Henares the formal dinner took place at the local restaurant

La Cúpula, which was the church of a convent in the XVII century.

6 Documents, Photos, Videos - Download

- **Handbook / Agenda:** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10018164>
- **Presentation slides (Zenodo):** <https://zenodo.org/communities/ggosdays2023/>
- **Photo Gallery:** <https://cloud.ggos.org/index.php/s/rNceKK6AZHGyy7j>
- **Recorded presentations (YouTube):**
<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLIIfsJS7iAuxuAmbz02IXTbSIHRtvBC7Q>

7 Meeting Organization

This meeting was chaired by the **GGOS President Laura Sánchez** (Deutsches Geodätisches Forschungsinstitut der Technischen Universität München, DGFI-TUM) and jointly planned by the **GGOS Coordination Office (Martin Sehnal)**, Bundesamt für Eich- und Vermessungswesen, BEV) and the **Local Organizing Committee** of the Spanish Instituto Geográfico Nacional (IGN), consisting of the following colleagues:

José Antonio López Fernández, Elena Martínez Sánchez, Esther Azcue Infanzón, Felipe Paredes Montalván, Leonor Cui Domingo Centeno, Víctor Puente García, Cristina García Miró, Beatriz Vaquero Jiménez, Aarón González Arriol

8 Participants

Members of the GGOS Governing Board, GGOS Bureaus, GGOS Focus Areas, GGOS Science Panel, invited guests and all interested persons were highly welcome to attend the GGOS Days 2023. In total, 192 colleagues attended the 2023 GGOS Days - 40 in person and 152 virtually. Looking at the individual days more closely, 89 people participated virtually on day 1, 123 on day 2 and 91 on day 3. This is an incredible number and shows the growing interest in the activities of GGOS, IAG and Geodesy. Many thanks to all participants for their interest.

40 In-Person Participants:

Name	Country of Work
Claudia Noemi Tocho	Argentina
Lena Steiner	Austria
Martin Sehnal	Austria
Daniela Thaller	Germany
Detlef Angermann	Germany
Ezequiel Darío Antokoletz	Germany
Harald Schuh	Germany
Hermann Drewes	Germany
Kirsten Elger	Germany
Laura Sanchez	Germany
Milad Asgarimehr	Germany
Basara Miyahara	Japan

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Toshimichi Otsubo	Japan
Yusuke Yokota	Japan
Cornelis Slobbe	Netherlands
Peter Teunissen	Netherlands
Luísa Magalhães	Portugal
Rossen Grebenitcharsky	Saudi Arabia
Agnes Sylvia Kallon	Sierra Leone
Aletha de Witt	South Africa
Marisa Nickola	South Africa
Andrés Calabia	Spain
Elena Martínez Sanchez	Spain
Esther Azcue	Spain
Isabel Vigo	Spain
Jose Antonio Lopez Fernandez	Spain
Jose Manuel FERRANDIZ	Spain
Luis del Peral	Spain
Manuel Angel Sánchez Piedra	Spain
Marcelino Valdés	Spain
Maria Karbon	Spain
Santiago Belda	Spain
Agbissoh Otote	Spain
Benedikt Soja	Switzerland
Allison Craddock	United States of America (USA)
Christopher DiLullo	United States of America (USA)
David Gordon	United States of America (USA)
Mike Pearlman	United States of America (USA)
Remington Oliver Sexton	United States of America (USA)
Richard Gross	United States of America (USA)

152 Virtual Participants:

Name	Country of Work
Mauricio A Gende	Argentina
Agustín Reynaldo Gómez	Argentina
Romina Galvan	Argentina
Anna Riddell	Australia
Ryan Ruddick	Australia
David Schunck	Australia
Lucia McCallum	Australia

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Luis Elneser	Australia
Gregor Moeller	Austria
Carine Bruyninx	Belgium
Eric Pottiaux	Belgium
Gabriel do Nascimento Guimarães	Brazil
Roberto Teixeira Luz	Brazil
Ana Matos	Brazil
Lyubka Pashova	Bulgaria
Stanislava Valcheva	Bulgaria
Sandra Bolanos	Canada
Barbara Cubillos	Chile
Hermes García Pérez	Chile
Ignacio Andres Parada Pichuante	Chile
Sergio Rozas Bornes	Chile
Haixia Lyu	China, People's Republic of
Kaifa Kuang	China, People's Republic of
Kosuke Heki	China, People's Republic of
Yuanwei Wu	China, People's Republic of
Dongshan Yin	China, People's Republic of
Haibo Que	China, People's Republic of
Maida Mojica	Colombia
Mauricio Varela Sánchez	Costa Rica
Saulimar Rodriguez Montilla	Dominica
Abdelrahim Ruby Abdelhamid Hassanain	Egypt
Melese Wondatir Sisay	Ethiopia
Fabricio Prol	Finland
Hannu Ruotsalainen	Finland
Jaakko Mäkinen	Finland
Markku Poutanen	Finland
Ulla Kallio	Finland
Junchen Xue	France
Laurent Soudarin	France
Michela Ravanelli	France
Alexander Kehm	Germany
Daixin Zhao	Germany
E. Sinem Ince	Germany

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Eri Stern	Germany
Hansjörg Kutterer	Germany
Jan Dostal	Germany
Jürgen Müller	Germany
Kyriakos Balidakis	Germany
Marvin Reich	Germany
Mohammad Omidalizarandi	Germany
Peter Steigenberger	Germany
Roland Pail	Germany
Sadegh Modiri	Germany
Anastasiia Walenta	Germany
Christina Dimopoulou	Germany
Claudia Flohrer	Germany
Hartmut Wziontek	Germany
Lilliane Biskupek	Germany
Lin Wang	Germany
Lisa Klemm	Germany
Michael Schmidt	Germany
Sabine Bachmann	Germany
Sarah Kowal	Germany
Sonja Geist	Germany
Thomas Gruber	Germany
Dimitros Anastasious	Greece
Rafailia-Maria Mavromatidou	Greece
Christopher Kotsakis	Greece
George Verogs	Greece
Arnab Laha	India
Abhishek Mhamane	India
Varuna Kumar Guddanti	India
Dr Ely	Iran
Riccardo Barzaghi	Italy
Rosa Pacione	Italy
Kensuke Kokado	Japan
Young Jin LEE	Korea, Republic of
Hasu Yoon	Korea, Republic of
Jānis Kaminskis	Latvia
Ahmed Imloul	Morocco

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Sandesh Upadhyaya	Nepal
Dimitrios Psychas	Netherlands
Lotfi Massarweh	Netherlands
Elisabetta D'Anastasio	New Zealand
Chukwuma Anoruo	Nigeria
Vladimir Basilio Sulca Ñahui	Peru
Krzysztof Sońnica	Poland
Dariusz Strugarek	Poland
Dorota Marjanska	Poland
Marcin Ligas	Poland
Przemyslaw Dykowski	Poland
Tomasz Kur	Poland
João Salmim Ferreira	Portugal
Manuela Vasconcelos	Portugal
Helena Ribeiro	Portugal
Zinovy Malkin	Russia
Sultan Falah Alshahrani	Saudi Arabia
Assumpció Termens	Spain
Bea Vaquero	Spain
Vicente Navarro	Spain
Víctor Puente	Spain
Iñigo Molina	Spain
Sonia Guessoum	Spain
Rebekka Steffen	Sweden
Karine Le Bail	Sweden
Urs Marti	Switzerland
Zouheir Fatnassi	Tunisia
Emel Zeray Öztürk	Turkey
Mehmet Arkalı	Turkey
Andy Matthews	United Kingdom
Simon Williams	United Kingdom
Alexander Sun	United States of America (USA)
Frank Lemoine	United States of America (USA)
Katarzyna Oldak Wong	United States of America (USA)
Maria Davis	United States of America (USA)
Nicholas Stamatakos	United States of America (USA)
Sharyl Byram	United States of America (USA)
Walter Humberto Subiza Pina	Uruguay

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Ryan Hippenstiel	USA
A Namazi	
Aaron Gonzalez	
Agbissoh Otote	
Anonym	
Betty Heller-Kaikov	
Chanmi Kim	
Cheng Pan	
Dang Yao	
Dirk Behrend	
Dzana Halilovic	
Elena Martinez Sanchez	
Holger Steffen	
Ingus	
Ira Anjasmara	
Jack McCubbine	
Javier	
Jerome Saunier	
Jim Antonisse	
José Antonio Tarrío	
José C. Rodríguez	
Junyang Gou	
Karen Sierra	
Kemin Zhu	
Marcelino Valdés	
Maria Jose	
Martyna	
Matthias Aichinger	
Renal	
Ruotsalainen Hannu	
Saniya Behzadpour	
UFZ-CHS	
Zyi	